

THE EFFECT OF LEADERSHIP STYLE AND COMPENSATION ON VILLAGE OFFICE PERFORMANCE WITH WORK MOTIVATION AS A MEDIATING VARIABLE IN SEVERAL VILLAGES IN MANTUP DISTRICT

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Abstract . This study aims to find empirical evidence whether leadership style and compensation influence performance through motivation on village officials in several villages in Mantup Districts . This study uses a quantitative type with an explanatory approach . The study uses primary data collected directly . The population is all village officials in Mantup District , with a purposive sampling technique obtained a sample of 36 villages officials working in Kedungsoko, Rumpuk, and Sumberbendo Villages , namely villages that have problems related to the performance of their village officials . Data were collected using a questionnaire technique , and processed using path analysis with the help of SmartPLS which consists of an evaluation of the measurement model to prove the instrument is valid and reliable ; and an evaluation of the structural model to prove the research hypothesis . The results of the study concluded that leadership style is a significant predictor that positively influences work motivation and performance of village officials . However , compensation is unable to influence work motivation or village performance officials . Work motivation is able to be significant predictor that positively influences performance .

Keywords : Leadership Style; Work Performance; Compensation ; Work Motivation ; Village Apparatus .

1. INTRODUCTION

A village is a governmental area within a country and is considered the smallest unit. A country's success in economic development must begin with village development, which is determined by the level of participation of the people and village officials in development. Given their crucial role, the primary actors driving and developing villages are village officials. official with good performance is one that is capable of managing the Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBD). This means that if the village official is negligent in managing the APBN, its performance can be said to be poor. This phenomenon of poor performance was previously revealed in the Indonesian Ombudsman's Report Settlement Management Information System (Simpel). Between 2020 and 2023, 375 out of 947 reports received from village communities related to the appointment and dismissal of village officials (Ombudsman, 2023) . This figure is quite high and raises concerns that the village government is not yet implementing transparent and accountable governance. A survey conducted by Indonesia Corruption Watch (ICW) in 2022 showed that since the disbursement of village funds, corruption has actually increased:

Table 1 Number of Corruption Cases in the Village Sector and Potential State Losses (2016-2022)

Year	Number of Cases	Potential Loss (Rp)
2016	17	40.1 Billion
2017	48	10.4 Billion
2018	83	19.4 Billion
2019	96	36.5 Billion
2020	129	50.1 Billion
2021	154	233 Billion
2022	155	381 Billion

Source: Databoks (2024) .

Table 1 shows that in 2016 there were 17 cases of corruption in village government. However, seven years later, the number of cases increased significantly to 155 cases, with total losses of Rp381 billion. Corruption in villages can be caused by five loopholes: biased interests of elite groups, nepotism and lack of transparency, mark-ups and manipulation, fictitious reports, and the potential for mere formality. If village officials have low competence,

the management of village funds is potentially susceptible to corruption. This case demonstrates that poorly performing work units can potentially lead to negligence in managing village funds and hinder development. Therefore, improving the performance of village officials is crucial. The primary factor influencing performance is leadership style. Leadership style is how a leader influences a group or its members (Mushaddiq Suaidy & Rony, 2023). Research by Mardani & Yansahrita (2024) and Marlina et al. (2024) shows that leadership style can influence the performance of village officials. Meanwhile, research by Komala et al. (2024) shows that leadership style is not a factor influencing the performance of village officials.

The second factor that can influence the performance of village officials is compensation. Compensation is a reward given by a company to employees for their efforts (Rozi et al., 2024). Research by Akhmad et al. (2023) and Ludin et al. (2023) shows that compensation can influence the performance of village officials. Meanwhile, research by Mulyana & Maulana (2023) indicates that compensation is not a factor that influences the performance of village officials. And the third factor influencing village apparatus performance is work motivation. Work motivation is a situation that stimulates, directs, and maintains behavior in relation to the work environment (Rozi et al., 2025). Research by Mamonto et al. (2024) and Rizqiyah et al. (2022) shows that motivation can influence village apparatus performance. Meanwhile, research by Lestari et al. (2025) shows that motivation is not a factor influencing village apparatus performance.

This study uses two dependent variables, in addition to village apparatus performance, namely motivation. The basis for choosing motivation as the second dependent variable is due to the inconsistent results of previous studies, and the assumption that good leadership style and compensation can increase motivation and encourage performance. A review of previous research shows that research by Anshori et al. (2022) and Santhi et al. (2024) shows that leadership style can influence the work motivation of village apparatus. Meanwhile, research by Saragih et al. (2025) shows that leadership style is not a factor that influences the work motivation of village apparatus. Then, research by Sanjaya et al. (2023) and Kamila et al. (2024) shows that compensation can influence the work motivation of village apparatus. Meanwhile, research by Ramdani & Murwaningsih (2026) shows that compensation is not a factor that influences the work motivation of village apparatus. This study examines village officials in Mantup District, specifically in the villages of Kedungsoko, Rumpuk, and Sumberbendo. The reason these three villages were chosen was because there were problems with the performance of village officials in each of them. In Kedungsoko village, the phenomenon that occurred was community disappointment with the poor performance of Village Head Mahfud Riyanto, SH, who was often absent from the village head's office and very difficult to meet. This had occurred repeatedly, even for months, and no firm sanctions were imposed (MPN, 2024).

Another phenomenon that occurred in Rumpuk Village was that the village head's office was often closed, even during working hours. This practice was even referred to as a habit, where village officials were often absent from the office and the office was closed for operations. According to the community, this constitutes a form of time wastage and an inability to provide public services (MPN, 2025). Finally, in Sumberbendo Village, there was a case of Collusion, Corruption, and Nepotism (KKN). This indication is based on the village head, Jumali.SE, when applying for the position of village head, promising positions to his campaign team. Some people even made a certain amount of money, but the positions were not certain when they would be given (RodaInformasi, 2023). These cases indicate that there are still village officials who have poor performance and are unable to serve the community.

This research is crucial due to the inconsistent results of previous studies and the presence of real problems such as low work discipline, weak public services, and indications of Collusion, Corruption, and Nepotism (KKN) practices. These conditions result in decreased work motivation, a suboptimal compensation system, and ultimately, low village apparatus performance. Based on this urgency, this study aims to find empirical evidence of whether leadership style and compensation influence performance through motivation among village apparatus in several villages in Mantup District.

2. THEORETICAL STUDY

Human Resources

According to Santoso (2025), human resources (HR) is an activity that essentially involves managing employees within an organization to achieve performance that meets the company's expectations. The concepts of HR management encompass needs planning, recruitment, training, and evaluation.

Village Apparatus Performance

According to Setiabudi et al. (2025), performance reflects the aspects of responsibility, participation, and initiative in completing work. Village apparatus performance is measured using the following indicators: work quality, work quantity, timeliness, effectiveness, and independence (Azizah et al., 2026)

Leadership Style

Leaders are a tool for managing employees so they can work effectively (Saputra & Rohmah, 2024) . Leadership style or type of leadership is an aspect that is greatly needed by organizations because of its ability to encourage employees to achieve targets and create a productive work environment. According to Syaikhudin et al. (2023), leadership style is the behavior of a leader in influencing subordinates, seen from the way they give orders and support so that all work tasks are completed and goals can be achieved. Measurement of leadership style uses indicators: decision-making ability, motivation ability, communication ability, and delegation of authority (Yuliarti & Mukhlis, 2023) .

Compensation

According to Rupus & Febrianto (2025) , compensation refers to any form of income, whether in kind or in-kind, received by employees. According to Qilmi et al. (2025), compensation plays a crucial role in improving performance because it is a reward employees receive for their work, and appropriate compensation will improve their performance. Compensation is measured using the following indicators: adequate salary, fairness of compensation, timely payment, and completeness of benefits (Zai et al., 2025) .

Work motivation

Motivation drives employees to perform well and orientate themselves toward the company's goals. Motivation is crucial for employees because of its positive impact on both the company and themselves, fostering work ethic and responsibility (Esisuarni et al., 2024) . Work motivation is measured using the following indicators: drive, direction, persistence, responsibility, and need for achievement (Yunus & Rocdianingrum, 2023) .

Previous Research

A review of previous research has been conducted in several studies. Research by Athapaththu & Rebecca (2025) , Dayanti & Prasajo (2020) , Mardani & Yansahrita (2024) , Marlina et al. (2024) , Anshori et al. (2022) , and Prasiska (2023) shows that leadership style is a predictor of village apparatus performance. Meanwhile, research by Komala et al. (2024) and Saragih et al. (2025) shows that leadership style is not a predictor of village apparatus performance. Research by Akhmad et al. (2023) , Sanjaya et al. (2023) , Ervina et al. (2023) , Ludin et al. (2023) , and Thapa (2023) shows that compensation is a predictor of village apparatus performance. Meanwhile, research by Mulyana & Maulana (2023) and Naldi et al. (2026) shows that compensation is not a predictor of village apparatus performance.

Research by Mamonto et al. (2024) , Anshori et al. (2022) , Naldi et al. (2026) , Saragih et al. (2025) , and Rizqiyah et al. (2022) shows that motivation is a predictor of village apparatus performance. Meanwhile, research by Ervina et al. (2023) , Lestari et al. (2025) , and Marlina et al. (2024) shows that motivation is not a predictor of village apparatus performance. Research by Athapaththu & Rebecca (2025) , Dayanti & Prasajo (2020) , Anshori et al. (2022) , and Santhi et al. (2024) shows that leadership style is a predictor of village officials' work motivation. Meanwhile, research by Saragih et al. (2025) shows that leadership style is not a predictor of village officials' work motivation. Research by Sanjaya et al. (2023) , Ervina et al. (2023) , Kamila et al. (2024) , Naldi et al. (2026) , and Thapa (2023) shows that compensation is a predictor of village officials' work motivation. However, Ramdani & Murwaningsih (2026) showed that compensation is not a predictor of village officials' work motivation.

The differences between previous research and this study lie in the variables, research model, and research object. Previous research generally only used leadership style, work discipline, communication, or work environment as independent variables, while this study uses leadership style and compensation with work motivation as the second dependent variable and as a variable that influences the performance of village officials. Furthermore, previous research has been mostly conducted in companies, hospitals, and government agencies, while this study focuses on village officials in Mantup District. Therefore, this study has a novel research model that lies in a more comprehensive research model by combining leadership style, compensation, work motivation, and village official performance. Furthermore, this study uses work motivation as both an independent and dependent variable and focuses on village officials in Mantup District, which is still rarely studied.

Framework of Thought and Hypothesis Development

Figure 1 Framework of Thought

Based on this framework of thought, the hypotheses developed in this study are as follows:

1. H_1 = Leadership style has a significant influence on work motivation.
2. H_2 = Compensation has a significant effect on work motivation
3. H_3 = Leadership style has a significant influence on village apparatus performance
4. H_4 = Compensation has a significant effect on Village Apparatus Performance
5. H_5 = Work motivation has a significant influence on village apparatus performance

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This study employed a quantitative approach with an explanatory approach. This research method was chosen because it aimed to identify the interrelationships between variables. The study was conducted in several villages in Mantup District, specifically Kedungsoko, Rumpuk, and Sumberbendo. These three villages were chosen over others due to the phenomenon of problems related to poor village apparatus performance. Therefore, it is necessary to examine whether this performance is influenced by leadership style, compensation, and work motivation.

The data in this study are primary data obtained by distributing questionnaires to village officials in selected villages. The population in this study was all village officials working in the village government in Mantup District. However, the sample studied was only 3 villages, this is based on the sampling technique using purposive sampling where the sample was selected with certain criteria, which in this study the criteria were villages reported by the media to have issues related to low performance. Based on these criteria, a total of 13 village officials were obtained in Kedungsoko Village, 12 village officials in Sumberbendo Village, and 11 village officials in Rumpuk Village. The total sample was 36 village officials. Data were collected using a questionnaire, using a 5-point Likert scale. Path analysis using SmartPLS was then used. This analysis involved evaluating the measurement model to test the validity and reliability of the instrument, and evaluating the structural model to verify the research hypotheses.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Outer Loading

Outer loading is used to test the validity of the research instrument. Ghazali (2022) requires that outer loading be accepted if the value is more than 0.6. In the first test, there were still invalid items, namely: X2.4 (0.580); X2.10 (0.511); X2.11 (0.547); X2.12 (0.396); X2.13 (0.418); Z1.13 (0.146); Z1.14 (0.393); Z1.15 (0.173). Invalid items were eliminated and retested.

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Table 2 Outer Results Loading

Variables	Item	Outer Loading Value	Conclusion
Leadership Style (X1)	1	0.675	VALID
	2	0.889	
	3	0.774	
	4	0.770	
	5	0.711	
	6	0.737	
	7	0.774	
	8	0.746	
	9	0.715	
	10	0.894	
	11	0.825	
	12	0.849	
	13	0.881	
	14	0.710	
	15	0.670	
	16	0.856	
	17	0.803	
	18	0.758	
	19	0.710	
	20	0.813	
Compensation (X2)	1	0.830	VALID
	2	0.823	
	3	0.744	
	5	0.826	
	6	0.814	
	7	0.871	
	8	0.886	
	9	0.731	
	1	0.851	
Village Apparatus Performance (Y)	2	0.639	VALID
	3	0.770	
	4	0.876	
	5	0.772	
	6	0.771	
	7	0.853	
	8	0.771	
	9	0.823	
	10	0.827	
	11	0.931	
	12	0.829	
	13	0.795	
	14	0.893	
	15	0.724	
	1	0.798	

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Variables	Item	Outer Loading Value	Conclusion
Work Motivation (Z)	2	0.780	
	3	0.852	
	4	0.768	
	5	0.792	
	6	0.846	
	7	0.921	
	8	0.796	
	9	0.846	
	10	0,000	
	11	0,000	
	12	0,000	

Table 2 shows that the outer loading values are satisfactory, all exceeding the 0.6 criteria, so that the assumption of the validity of the outer loading is met.

Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

In SmartPLS testing, the AVE must also be met for the instrument to be considered valid. The acceptance criterion for an AVE is that it must be greater than 0.5.

Table 3 AVE Results

Variables	AVE	Criteria	Information
Leadership Style (X1)	0.610		
Compensation (X2)	0.668		
Village Apparatus Performance (Y)	0.658	0.500	Reliable
Work Motivation (Z)	0.656		

Table 3 shows that the values are greater than 0.5. This figure is satisfactory because it confirms that the instrument is valid based on the AVE value.

Fornell-Lacker Criterion

Fornell Lacker criterion value is that the square root of the construct must be greater than the square root of the other variable constructs.

Table 4 Fornell Lacker Criterion Results

	X1	Y	X2	Z
Leadership Style (X1)	0.781			
Village Apparatus Performance (Y)	0.627	0.811		
Compensation (X2)	0.860	0.473	0.877	
Work Motivation (Z)	0.599	0.889	0.469	0.910

Table 4 shows that the square root value of each variable is greater than the other variables. Therefore, the test requirements are met and can be considered valid.

Cross Loading

Having similarities with Fornell Lacker , the acceptance requirement for cross loading is that it has a value greater than the indicator value of other variables to be said to be valid.

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Table 5 Cross Loading Results

Variables	Item	X1	X2	Y	Z
Leadership Style (X1)	1	0.675	0.691	0.183	0.174
	2	0.889	0.763	0.541	0.530
	3	0.774	0.618	0.529	0.522
	4	0.770	0.640	0.579	0.559
	5	0.711	0.599	0.466	0.458
	6	0.737	0.582	0.371	0.337
	7	0.774	0.629	0.580	0.558
	8	0.746	0.585	0.305	0.273
	9	0.715	0.791	0.351	0.335
	10	0.894	0.804	0.536	0.517
	11	0.825	0.726	0.481	0.459
	12	0.849	0.795	0.505	0.499
	13	0.881	0.853	0.502	0.476
	14	0.710	0.569	0.594	0.576
	15	0.670	0.431	0.611	0.547
	16	0.856	0.790	0.502	0.484
	17	0.803	0.638	0.472	0.456
	18	0.758	0.646	0.395	0.359
	19	0.710	0.669	0.377	0.347
	20	0.813	0.699	0.475	0.441
Compensation (X2)	1	0.759	0.830	0.535	0.552
	2	0.733	0.823	0.378	0.383
	3	0.595	0.744	0.353	0.339
	5	0.860	0.826	0.475	0.454
	6	0.592	0.814	0.261	0.257
	7	0.729	0.871	0.321	0.309
	8	0.694	0.886	0.337	0.336
	9	0.503	0.731	0.252	0.247
	1	0.771	0.664	0.851	0.824
Village Apparatus Performance (Y)	2	0.558	0.416	0.639	0.618
	3	0.391	0.286	0.770	0.749
	4	0.493	0.311	0.876	0.835
	5	0.278	0.228	0.772	0.798
	6	0.391	0.249	0.771	0.794
	7	0.442	0.292	0.853	0.867
	8	0.631	0.607	0.771	0.778
	9	0.625	0.495	0.823	0.817
	10	0.429	0.298	0.827	0.828
	11	0.446	0.318	0.931	0.929
	12	0.720	0.589	0.829	0.814
	13	0.488	0.402	0.795	0.780
	14	0.622	0.448	0.893	0.866
	15	0.345	0.145	0.724	0.696
		1	0.278	0.228	0.772

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Variables	Item	X1	X2	Y	Z
Work Motivation (Z)	2	0.371	0.232	0.750	0.780
	3	0.422	0.275	0.832	0.852
	4	0.613	0.583	0.763	0.768
	5	0.601	0.492	0.790	0.792
	6	0.433	0.320	0.833	0.846
	7	0.434	0.301	0.917	0.921
	8	0.698	0.564	0.796	0.796
	9	0.516	0.470	0.836	0.846
	10	0.651	0.516	0.934	0.934
	11	0.367	0.208	0.742	0.732
	12	0.292	0.246	0.590	0.601

Based on table 5, each indicator and its variables have met the requirements, namely they are greater than the indicators of other variables, so the data is considered valid.

Reliability Test

Reliability testing by looking at the Cronbach Alpha and Composite Reliability values. The instrument is declared reliable if the value is more than 0.7 , the following are the test results:

Table 6 Reliability Results

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Criteria	Information
X2	0.966	0.969	0.700	Reliable
X2	0.931	0.941		
Y	0.962	0.966		
Z	0.951	0.958		

the Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values were each greater than 0.7. Therefore, it is concluded that the instrument in this study is reliable.

Coefficients of Determination (R2)

The R2 test was conducted to determine the extent of influence of the predictors on village apparatus performance. The criteria are divided into three categories: 0.75 is considered strong, 0.50 is considered moderate, and 0.25 is considered weak.

Table 7 R2 Results

	R Square	Category
Village Apparatus Performance (Y)	0.983	Strong
Work Motivation (Z)	0.366	Weak

Table 7 shows the R2 results. For the village apparatus performance variable (Y), the value is 0.983 (98.3%), meaning that leadership style and compensation are strong predictors of improving village apparatus performance. Furthermore, for the work motivation variable (Z), the value is 0.366 (36.6%), meaning that leadership style and compensation are weak predictors of improving village apparatus work motivation.

Effect Size (f2)

In multiple linear regression analysis, the F2 test is used to assess the influence of all predictors on the dependent variable. Therefore, a higher value indicates a greater effect. The categories 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 represent small, medium, and large effects, respectively.

Table 8F2 Results

	Z	Category	Y	Category
Leadership Style (X1)	0.231	Currently	0.221	Currently
Compensation (X2)	0.013	Small	0.115	Currently
Work Motivation (Z)			33,199	Big

Table 8 shows that leadership style is a moderate predictor of work motivation, while compensation is a small predictor of work motivation. Further results also show that leadership style is a moderate predictor of performance, and compensation is a medium predictor of performance. Meanwhile, work motivation is a large predictor of performance.

Path Coefficient

The path coefficient is a test used to assess research results and answer hypotheses. The criteria for accepting a hypothesis are that the calculated t-value must be greater than the t-table, and the p-value must be less than 5% or 0.05. The following is the research model:

Figure 2 Research Model

After attaching the research model, a table of the path coefficient test results is attached . The criterion for accepting the path coefficient is that the p-value or significance level must be less than 5% or 0.05. The following are the results of the path coefficient test , which can be used for hypothesis analysis:

Table 9Path Coefficient Results

Hypothesis	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values	Conclusion
H1	0.748	3,599	0,000	Accepted
H2	-0.174	0.621	0.535	Rejected
H3	0.134	2,022	0.044	Accepted
H4	-0.088	1,561	0.119	Rejected
H5	0.950	21,223	0,000	Accepted

Discussion

The Influence of Leadership Style on Work Motivation

The study showed a positive original sample value of 0.748, t count 3.599 > 2.032, p value 0.000 < 0.05. It was concluded that H1 was accepted and leadership style was able to influence work motivation positively and significantly. In line with the research of Athapaththu & Rebecca (2025) , Dayanti & Prasojo (2020) , Anshori et al. (2022) , Santhi et al. (2024) that the better the leadership style of a village head was able to increase the work

motivation of all village officials. A good leader is demonstrated by his ability to provide direction, support employees, and provide positive appreciation to trigger high work motivation.

The Influence of Compensation on Work Motivation

The study showed a negative original sample value of -0.174, t count $0.621 < 2.032$, p value $0.535 > 0.05$. It was concluded that H2 was rejected and compensation was unable to influence work motivation. In line with the research of Ramdani & Murwaningsih (2026), the results of the study indicate that the work motivation of village officials tends not to be formed due to compensation factors, but rather is driven by internal factors such as commitment, responsibility, the desire to provide good service, and the drive to achieve organizational goals. Although compensation is provided, it has not been the main factor capable of increasing respondents' work motivation in carrying out their duties.

The Influence of Leadership Style on Village Apparatus Performance

The study showed a positive original sample value of 0.135, t count $2.022 < 2.032$, p value $0.044 < 0.05$. It was concluded that H3 was accepted and leadership style was able to influence performance positively and significantly. In line with the research of Athapaththu & Rebecca (2025), Dayanti & Prasajo (2020), Mardani & Yansahrita (2024), Marlina et al. (2024), Anshori et al. (2022), Prasiska (2023) that if the village head is able to build solid working relationships and smooth coordination, the overall performance of the village apparatus will improve. However, the calculated t value is smaller than the t table, indicating that although the application of a good leadership style can encourage increased performance, the magnitude of the influence is relatively small, so there are other factors that may play a role in determining the level of performance of the village apparatus.

The Influence of Compensation on Village Apparatus Performance

The study showed a negative original sample value of -0.088, t-test $1.561 < 2.032$, p-value $0.119 > 0.05$. It was concluded that H4 was rejected and compensation was unable to affect performance. This is in line with research by Mulyana & Maulana (2023) and Naldi et al. (2026). These results indicate that the compensation received may have been viewed as a routine right or obligation and therefore not a primary driver for improving performance. Consequently, changes in compensation have not yet resulted in significant changes in the performance of village officials.

The Influence of Motivation on Village Apparatus Performance

The study showed a positive original sample value of 0.950, t count $21.223 < 2.032$, p value $0.000 < 0.05$. It was concluded that H5 was accepted and motivation was able to influence performance positively and significantly. In line with the research of Mamonto et al. (2024), Anshori et al. (2022), Naldi et al. (2026), Saragih et al. (2025) This study was conducted with the aim of evaluating the influence of leadership style and communication on employee performance, with work motivation as an intervening variable among employees of Aroma Bakery. The number of respondents in this study was 35 individuals. The sampling technique used was total sampling. This research is a causal-explanatory study, which explains the position of the variables studied as well as the influence between one variable and another. The data analysis used in this study is quantitative analysis using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) with SmartPLS. The results of the study show that: Leadership style has no effect on employee performance. Leadership style has no effect on work motivation. Communication has no effect on employee performance. Communication has no effect on work motivation. Work motivation has a significant effect on employee performance. Leadership style has no effect on employee performance with work motivation as an intervening variable. Communication has no effect on employee performance with work motivation as an intervening variable. Rizqiyah et al. (2022) the higher the work motivation of village officials, the higher the resulting performance. Motivation is an aspect that encourages someone to work well, so that village officials who have high motivation tend to work more diligently, have initiative in completing tasks, are responsible for their work, and provide more transparent services to the community. The very high coefficient or original sample value also indicates that motivation is a dominant factor in influencing the performance of village officials in this study.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Research shows that improving leadership style can be a predictor of increased work motivation and performance among village officials. However, compensation is not able to increase work motivation or performance among village officials. Increased work motivation also appears to be a predictor of improved performance. Findings

showing that compensation largely rejected the hypothesis, meaning that work motivation and performance among village officials are influenced by non-financial predictors. Therefore, efforts to improve village official performance should focus on strengthening the leadership quality of village heads, providing clear direction, providing work support, appreciating performance, and creating a work environment that fosters high work motivation.

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